

1 **Metabolic vulnerability in the circulating tumor cell.**

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6 Cellular metabolism is fundamentally dysregulated in human cancer, in the primary tumor, but how it
7 changes during dissemination in the migrating tumor cell in the periphery is not completely understood.
8 We describe activation of genes encoding metabolic pathway function including *ACOXL*, *PFKFB1*, and
9 *GFOD1* in the circulating tumor cell isolated from the peripheral blood of humans with stage IV cancer.
10 Metabolic derangement can also be observed in the circulating tumor cell.

11 Citations

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